

New Technology in Agriculture and Manufacturing Sectors in Nigeria

Felix I. Ifada

*Department of Economics
Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State.
ifadafelixy@gmail.com / 08038709737*

Prof. K. E. Uma

*Department of Economics
Alex Ekwueme Federal University
Ndufu Alike Ikwo, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State.
kaluskyebng@yahoo.com / 08036061790*

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21181757>

Abstract

This study is an investigation on the essence of New Technology in Agriculture and Manufacturing sectors in Nigeria. The source of data information were mainly online source, libraries/textbooks etc. The method of analysis includes the use of verbal and geometrical statements such as tables and charts. The analysis shows that New Technology in Agriculture/Manufacturing sectors has improved the production possibilities of some selected countries compared to Nigeria agricultural production. Such as United States of America, China, Brazil etc. as the largest producers of selected crops e.g. maize, wheat, rice etc. in the world production. The study recommends an aggressive pursuit of new technology, technological knowhow including mechanization of the agricultural and the manufacturing sectors. Modalities should be put in place to imbibe with the New Technology and mechanization of the agricultural system. Also, the government should provide an enabling environment for the unemployed youth to find a place in the agricultural sector and improve food production in the economy.

Key words: New Technology, Agriculture, Manufacturing, Nigeria, United States of America.

1.1 Introduction

The agricultural sector has been the mainstay of Nigerian economy. Despite several challenges being face by this all important sector, it remains the major sustainer of the populace. By 1960 Nigeria was tagged to be the world largest exporter of groundnut, the second largest exporter of cocoa and palm produce and an exporter of rubber, cotton (Sekunmade, 2009). In terms of employment, agricultural sector employs about two-thirds of Nigeria's working population, it contributes significantly to the GDP and provides a large proportion of the non-oil earnings (CIA, 2013; Sekunmade, 2009).

As a matter of fact, this sector has several untapped potential for growth and development in the availability of land, water, labour and its large internal markets. It is estimated that about 84million hectares of Nigeria's total land area has the potential for agricultural activities but only about 40% of this is being cultivated (FMARD, 2012). Productivity is low due to primitive farming methods and technological backwardness. It quite alarming and disappointing that Nigeria has become heavily dependent on food importation despite these great potentials. The sector has the potential for irrigation with a surface and underground water of about 267.7billion cubic metres and

57.9billion cubic metres respectively. (Chauvin, Mulangu and Porto, 2012; Lipton 2012). Nigeria's large and growing population provides a potential for a vibrant internal market for increased agricultural productivity. In spite of these potentials, the agricultural sector in Nigeria remains poor and largely underdeveloped. This has reflected negatively on the productivity of the sector, its contribution to economic growth and development as well as in the performance of its major role in terms of food production among others.

However, the dwindling nature of the sector has been blamed on oil glut and its consequences on several occasions (Falola and Haton, 2008).

According to Download Report, National Bureau of Statistics (2023) and Food Agricultural Organization (FAO), Nigeria at a glance, over 70% of Nigerians engage in agricultural sector mainly at local consumption level. Despite the contribution to the economy, it faces many problems and obstacles such as to poor land tenure system, poor irrigation farming and climatic change, land degradation problem, low level technology, others are high cost of production and inefficient distribution of inputs, lack of finance (credit facilities) post-harvest problem due to poor storage, lack of accessibility to market etc.

These challenges have hampered agricultural productivity and its contribution to the country's GDP as well as increase in the importation of food to cater for the increasing population. For instance between 2016 and 2019 Nigeria cumulative agricultural imports was #3.35trillion four times higher than the agricultural export of #803billion within the same period.

Several policies and efforts have been put in place as will see later in this section aim to increase agricultural productivity to ensure sufficient quantities of food for domestic consumption and export to other countries. More recently, is the Nigeria African Trade and Investment promotion programme, Agricultural promotion policy (APP) Export Promotion Incentive etc.

Nigeria has 70.8million hectares of agricultural land area with crop production as the dominant sub-sector. Rice production increased from 3.7million metric tons in 2017 to 4.0millions metric tons in 2018. Out of about 6.7million metric tons of the rice consumed in Nigeria annually, it is only 57% that is locally (domestically) produced in Nigeria with a shortage of about 3million metric tons which is either imported or smuggled into the country illegally.

Government banned importation of rice in 2019 in order to stimulate or encourage local production. For Cassava Nigeria produced about 59million tons in 2017 i.e. 20% of global production which ranked Nigeria, the world largest producer of cassava. The economic potentials of cassava is enormous.

The potentials for animal production (livestock) is under-utilized. This sub-sector is mostly neared by farm families in Nigeria. e.g. goats (76million), sheep (43.3million) and cattle (18.4million). Small and large ruminants of poultry population total about 180millions poultry (FMARD 2017). Again, local demand outweighs local production despite several interventions by development partners to improve production about 3.2million of fish is consumed by Nigerians annually. Nigeria has been ranked as the largest fish consumers in Africa and among the largest fish consumer in the World. Fisheries and aquaculture are among the fastest growing sub-sectors in the country. With a coast line of 853km and over 14million hectares of inland waters, there is almost 1million metric tons (313,231 metric ton) from aqua culture and (759,828 metric tons from

fisheries) as total fish production per year. This sub-sector is a viable alternative to meeting the nations need for self-sufficiency in fish production and nutritional needs.

According to FAO 2018, Report, annual deforestation rate is between 0.72% and 2.38%. Agricultural expansion, heavy reliance on firewood and charcoal for energy, unsustainable timber extraction, urbanization, grazing, bush fire, infrastructural development are among the factors responsible for this trend.

1.2 CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

New technology and technical knowhow:

There are two senses in which the term technology is used in literature – Broad view and Narrow view.

Broad View: Viewed broadly, technology is defined as cultural traditions developed in a human community for meeting the needs of the society. These traditions includes the practical skills involved in many activities of the community, e.g. hunting, agriculture, construction, transportation and communication and the provision of energy and health care services.

Narrow View: Technology is viewed in the narrow sense as the knowledge and information needed for doing something. Knowledge of how to do something including knowledge of necessary inputs. The skills and the procedures by which the inputs are transformed into the desire output. It also include the knowledge and skills needed for designing and fabricating the relevant items of equipment e.g. (the relevant machines and tools) and for designing and installing the factory. The paper production technology for example will involve the following.

- The knowledge of the input needed for producing paper
- The procedures by which the inputs are transformed into the desired paper
- The knowledge and skills needed for designing and fabricating paper production machines and tools and for designing and installing the factory
- The knowledge and skills needed for bringing the inputs together and transforming them into the desired output paper.

Technology is thus basically knowledge and skills require for doing things hence. Some people sometimes refer to it as “know how”. The narrow view of technology is précised and this is the most common use of term. For instance, when we talk of garri production technology or the ogogoro production technology or the shoe making technology, it should be very clear what is meant. This clearly is important in any effort to develop or acquire technologies.

Technology may also be defined as a set of techniques available for carrying out a particular activity. This boils down to the same thing as knowledge and skills. Technology is a collection of techniques while techniques means special way of doing something.

Technology is one of the major driving force of development. Whether the purpose is to produce food or more food, provide better education, improve health care, increase industrial output or to provide more effective and efficient transportation and communication systems, technology plays an important part, in fact, the key part as shown, technology creates the goods and services needed for survival and growth and its promotes efficiency in the provision of goods and services.

In today's world, it is technological capability that distinguishes a strong economy from a weak economy and a strong country from a weak country. A country cannot make a major stride without technological capabilities. Technology usually emerges from attempts to solve specific problems in particular social economic environment. They therefore generally have the characteristics of the environment in which they are developed. Examples of the characteristics are the nature and quality of inputs (including labour infrastructural services and the legal administrative system requires for successful operation. This is why it is also often argued that technology incorporates, reflects and perpetuates value system of the country.

Technologies are strong agent of change but the nature of the change that result from the application of a particular technology will depend on the characteristics of the technology. A country can develop a labour saving technology. India went in for cottage industry – medium and large scale enterprises.

From the introductory part of the agricultural sector, it is crystal clear that the agricultural sector has been the main stay of the Nigerian economy despite the challenges being faced by this sector. This is evident through food supply, job generation, provision of raw materials for our industries, and its contribution to the growth and development of the economy. The major components of agricultural sector include crops production, livestock, fishery and forestry. These sub-sectors have the potentials that give the country an opportunity for growth and development. The issue of New Technology in agricultural production cannot be over emphasized.

2.1 THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Agricultural Policies, Reforms and Implementation in Focus

In order to revamp the agricultural sector, the federal government had embarked on and implemented several agricultural policies and programmes, some of which are defunct or abandoned, and some restructured while others are still in place.

These include the farm settlement schemes, National Accelerated Food Production (NAFPP), Agricultural Development Projects (ADPs) River Basin Development Authorities (RBDAs) etc to mention but a few.

The federal Government in 2004 launched another economic reform called National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS) programme to encourage private sector participation in the development of the economy. It was also aimed at promoting growth and poverty reduction. NEEDS was short lived for only one year and therefore could not transform or make significant impact on the sector.

Again there were different strategies adopted by the country which shows dynamism and changing strategies to implement agricultural policies designed at different time periods. According to Olayemi (1998), such strategies can be categorized into,

- **Exploitative strategy:** The Nigerian Government during the colonial period and early years of independence adopted this strategy for agricultural development. This was a strategy in the 1950's and 1960's in Nigeria with levies on export crops providing revenue for government to develop the modern sector (Adubi, 2004).
- **Agricultural project strategy:** This period coincided with the time of internal self government up till 1968. Government intervention in agriculture was minimal. The small scale farmers

in Nigeria bore the brunt of agricultural development efforts (Egwu and Akubuilu, 2007). Agricultural sector was seen as a sector to provide the needed forward and backward linkages to other sectors for growth and development.

- Direct government production strategy: According to Olayemi (1998), this was merely a deepening of the process of direct government intervention and investment in agriculture. This period started in 1970 and coincided with the oil boom in Nigeria.
- Integrated rural development strategy: In the mid – 1970s, when the government realized that the direct agricultural production strategy was not yielding the desired results, the integrated rural development strategy was introduced.

According to (Olayemi, 1998), rural development was seen from a holistic perspective with agricultural development problems being seen as an integral part of development concerns. This prompted the government to embark on rural development programmes and implementing institutions such as Agricultural Development Projects (ADPs), The River Basin Development Authorities (RBDAs), the Directorate of Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI), Operation Feed the Nation (OFN), The Green Revolution (GR) etc. This strategy was also extended to the era of Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1985-86) but with significant changes in institutional design, intensity of activities and modes of operation.

However, the assessment of the effects of the agricultural reforms policies on the agricultural sector is with respect to fundamental roles of agriculture, namely

- Provision of adequate food for a growing population, raw materials for industries.
- Provision for an expanding market for non-agricultural products.
- Generation of savings for investment in agriculture as well as other sectors and release surplus or under utilized resources to other sectors in the economy.
- Generation of foreign exchange earning.

Let briefly look at the various periods of the government intervention in the development of agricultural production in Nigeria.

- i. The 1969 era (period of minimum government intervention). In this era of minimal government intervention, the small scale farmers in Nigeria bore the brunt of agricultural development efforts (Egwu and Akubuilu, 2007). According to Olayemi (1995) government effort took the form of settling policies and creating institutions for agricultural research, extension and export crop marketing and pricing. During this period agriculture contributes about 56% GDP in the 1960's with about 63% in the half of the decade, while the foreign exchange earnings declined from 71% in 1964 to 41% in 1969.
- ii. The 1970 to 1985 era (period of maximum government intervention). During this period the oil boom featured, which brought about enormous financial investment in agricultural projects and institutions. The fiscal monetary and trade policies under the macro economic policies were launched during this period e.g.

Fiscal Policy: budgetary allocations to agriculture were substantially increased to accommodate capital and recurrent expenditures. Large deficits were recorded. The capital expenditure on agriculture decline from 6.2% in 1973 to 4.0% in 1985. This was also applicable to the state government for the period under review (Egwu and Akubuilu, 2007).

Monetary policy: Agricultural loans were given at concessionary interest rate of 6% per annum. It was raised to 9% per annum in 1980s.

There were also establishment of schemes and institutions e.g. The Nigerian Agricultural and Cooperative Bank (NACB) established in 1973 to facilitate the granting of credit to Nigerian farmers.

Mandatory sectoral allocation to agriculture: Commercial and Merchant Banks were mandated to extend a minimum of 6% of their loan portfolio to agriculture which was later increased to 12% Rural Banking Scheme was launched in 1977. Agricultural credit guarantee scheme was established in 1977. Trade policy on abolition of export duties in 1973 in order to promote agricultural export trade. Again there were also wage policy and income tax reliefs of income from new agricultural enterprises.

These were good policies and strategies for agricultural development, but then no significant impact has been made beyond subsistence farming and small scale agricultural production in Nigeria. This is the more reason why Nigeria still import most food items to supplement her domestic production. For instance, if this period was characterized as maximum government intervention in agriculture, why is the decline in capital expenditure on agriculture from 6.2% in 1973 to 4.0% in 1985? It means capital intensive mode of agricultural productions was neglected during the period under review. Essentially, capital intensive mode of production centered around New technology and technological innovations in agricultural against the use of crude implements in agricultural sector. New Technology and technological knowhow is crucial in this section of book for Research work. The 1985 to 1990 era (Structural Adjustment Programmes (SAP) and post SAP period. The era witnessed the Federal Ministry of Agriculture, water resources and rural development in 1988, produced an agricultural policy for Nigeria decree to be operational for at least next fifteen years.

There were policies and strategies on food crops, livestock and fish production industrial raw materials (crop and by products) production, and forest products and wildlife. Also policies on agricultural extension, technology development and transfer, agricultural credit, agricultural insurance agricultural mechanization, water resources development etc.

With the adoption of structural adjustment programme (SAP) in 1986, government admitted the failure of past policies to significantly improve the economy and reverse the declining trend of production in the agricultural sector. Hence, the SAP objectives (Adubi, 2004) include;

- i. Achieve fiscal stability and balance of payments viability over the medium term and
- ii. Promote economic growth with single digit inflation rates.

The government intention to achieve this is to stimulate domestic production and broaden the supply of the economy production and the supply base of the economy, Liberalization of trade and export controls, elimination of price control and commodity boards, decontrol of interest rate and

further rationalization and restructuring of the tariffs to smooth the way toward industrial diversification (Sanyal et al, 2010).

Despite all these measures no significant over all growth was recorded. There was a reduction in export earnings to less than 5% widening gap in food supply and demand food prices increased from 2.6% in 1970 to 1979 period to almost 20% during 1980-1989. There was lower agricultural and economic growth with high rates of unemployment.

2.2 THE NEW MILLENNIUM AGRICULTURAL POLICIES (1999-2009)

At the beginning of the new democratic administration in May, 1999 and shortly before then, there were a lot of changes introduced in order to realized the sectors objectives and in line with the tendency that agricultural and rural development were crucial for improved economic recovery (Olomola, 1998) many of the existing ministries, reforms and policies were prescribed and re-enacted.

The new agricultural policy has a clear statement of objectives. The policy seeks to attain self sustaining growth in all the sub-sectors of agriculture and the structural transformation necessary for the overall socio-economic development of the country as well as the improvement of the quality of life of Nigerians. It major objectives include;

- i. Attainment of self sufficiency in basic food commodities
- ii. Increase in local production of agricultural raw materials to meet the growth of an expanding industrial sector
- iii. Increase in production and procession of exportable commodities
- iv. Modernization of agricultural production, processing, storage and distribution through the infusion of improved technologies and management so that agriculture can be more responsive to the demands of other sectors of Nigerian economy.
- v. Creation of more agricultural and rural empowerment/ employment opportunities as to increase income of farmers and rural dwellers and productivity absorb an increasing labour force in the nation.

This phase among other things witnessed dramatic reduction in food importation from 14.5% to 5% of total imports, presidential initiatives on specific agricultural commodities, cassava, rice etc in order to generate #3billion annually from export. Though there were a lot of defects of these policy measures, Nigerian agriculture recorded good growth rates in the recent past with growth rates of 7.4, 7.2 and 6.5% in 2006, 2007 and 2008 respectively.

Between 2003 and 2007 its average share of the national real GDP was 41.5% thus underscoring its importance in the livelihood of Nigerians (FGN, undated) of the growth in 2003, to 2007 period, the crop, livestock, fishery and fishery sub-sectors contributed 90, 6, 3 and 1% respectively to GDP. The major crops in Nigeria include Yam, Cassava, Sorghum, Millet, Rice, Maize, Beans, Dried Cowpea, Groundnut, Cocoyam and Sweet Potato.

These major crops which accounted for about 75% of total crop sales in 2004 increased from 81,276 thousand tones in 2004 to 95,556 thousand tones in 2007 (Ego, 2008).

The manufacturing sector is complementary to the agricultural sector as far as the Nigerian concern. From the introductory aspect of this section of the book, manufacturing has been seen as the production of goods and services for the use of mankind or for sales. For viability, productive manufacturing and industrial sector, innovations, new technology are crucial factors for growth and development of the economy, hence the issue of new technology is paramount in the discussion of agricultural and manufacturing sectors in Nigeria.

According to Ministry of Budget and National Planning (2017), on Nigeria Economic Recovery and Growth Plan, the Nigeria industrial Revolution Plan (NIRP) was formed to accelerate the build-up of industrial capacity within Nigeria. Four groups of industries where Nigeria already possess a clear comparative advantage include;

- i. **Agric – Business and Agro Allied:** This is intended to build an end-to-end integrated agriculture value chain boosting local production to meet local demand thereby reducing the country's reliance on Imports of processed food products.
- ii. **Solid minerals and metals:** This is to create a favourable environment targeting large scale investors to institutionalize world class production standards in the country's solid minerals sectors.
- iii. **Oil and gas related industries:** Provide opportunity for Nigeria to build competitive oil and gas driven industries, encourage high value adding down streams investment and build institutional industrial strength within the country.
- iv. **Construction, light manufacturing and services:** leverages the significant opportunities in local markets. For construction (i.e. housing) light manufacturing and services offered by Nigeria's large consumer population, business demands and infrastructure needs.

2.3 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AGRICULTURAL SECTOR AND MANUFACTURING SECTOR

The relationship between agricultural sector and manufacturing sectors is linked with the forward and backward linkage of the agricultural sector and the manufacturing sector. It means that agricultural sector can serve as feeder pillar in terms of raw materials and industrial inputs to the manufacturing and industrial sectors. This is imperative to New Technology than going to other countries to source for raw materials for the industries to thrive. The forward linkage is on the aspects of job creation for the teaming population both in the agricultural sector, manufacturing and industrial sector as well.

Thus the agricultural sector serve as a feeder pillar to the manufacturing sector as source of raw materials to the industries. While the industrial sector also serve as an avenue for marketing the agricultural products as semi-finished products. The co-existence of these sectors will provide a soft landing for New Technology to thrive.

New Technology in agricultural productivity growth requires fostering the linkages between the agricultural and non-agricultural sectors. According to Adelman (1984), because of the strong growth linkages effects, agricultural development can lead to a wider economic growth in many countries even open economies during the early stages of industrialization. Carvantes –Godoy and Dewbree (2010) are also of the view that agricultural development plays a vital role in poverty reduction and economic transformation. It reduces poverty through direct impacts on farm incomes

and employment while indirect impacts are through linkages. The importance of intersectional linkage in the growth process had been widely recognized. According to Adegeye and Ditto (1985) agricultural output can increase the level of income of farmers and the people.

According to National Bureau of Statistics (2011), GDP Reports. In recent times, agricultural sector maintains the largest sector in the economy with its contribution to GDP. According to data from National Bureau of Statistics on fourth quarter 2021 GDP report. In 2021, agricultural sector contributed 25.9% with estimated value of #18.74trillion to GDP. It grew year by year by 2.1% from 18.35trillion recorded in the previous year. On a broader spectrum service sector contributed 53.56% to Nigeria GDP uptick compound to 52.44% recorded in the previous year. Industrial sector dropped to 20.56% from 21.36% recorded in 2020.

In 2022, the contribution of the agricultural sector to GDP dropped to 23.69% from 25.9% previous year the service sector dropped to 44.04% from 53.56% recorded in the previous year while the industrial sector increased to 30.78% from the record of previous year. Other sectors put together is 11.49% in the year 2022.

However, agricultural sector is very much below expectation despite numerous intervention by CBN, agricultural imports is still taking a significant amount of our foreign exchange reserves without significant inflow in terms of exchange earning.

In the year 2021, the various components of agriculture shows that crop production -#16.92trillion, livestock - #1.24trillion, forestry - #193.22billion and fishing - #384.45billion. other sectors in terms of its contribution include trade – 15.7%, information and communication – 15.5% with value of #11.23trillion in 2021 which represents 6.53% expansion compared to #10.54trillion recorded in previous year. Manufacturing sector – 9% with value of #6.5trillion increasing by 3.35% year on year from #6.29trillion recorded in the past year.

The manufacturing sector has about 12 components sub-sector – Oil refining, Cement manufacturing, Food, Textile production etc. this sector is mainly dominated by food production which value #3.18trillion, beverages and tobacco, and the #1.32trillion for cement industry. The manufacturing sector is retarded by the double figure contraction of the oil refining sub-sector of the economy.

Other sector with over 5% contribution to GDP include mining and quarrying (7.4%) and Real Estate (5.6%) etc.

3.1 PRESENTATION OF DATA ANALYSIS

Figure 3.1 A closer look at Nigeria agricultural sector and some selected countries in the world agriculture production.

Source: Economic Research Service (ERS) An official website of the United State Government, complemented by Food Dollar Series data product.

Online: <https://www.ers.usda.gov>.

Having examined the various sub-sectors of the Nigerian agriculture sector, we shall briefly look at the agricultural sector of some selected countries in the World agricultural production, such countries include; United State of America, India, Russia, Brazil, China.

Table 3.1 Global Ranking of Largest Producer of Selected Crops in World Production

Crops	1 st largest producer	2 nd largest producer	3 rd largest producer	4 th largest producer	5 th largest producer	6 th largest producer
Maize	USA	China and India	Brazil			
Wheat	China	India	USA	Russia		
Rice	China	India	Indonesia			
Potatoes	China	-	Russia	-	USA	India
Sugar Cane	Brazil	India	China			
Cassava	Nigeria					
Banana	India	China	Philippines			
Beef	Brazil	USA	China			

Source: Economic Research Service (ERS). An official website of the United State government and authors computation, 2024.

Online source: <https://www.investopedia.com>, <https://www.ers.usda.gov>
<https://www.llta.org/cropsnew/cassava/>

According to the latest data from the food and agricultural organization of the United Nations Statistics Division (FAOSTAT) with graphs, charts ranking and analysis, the USA is the World’s Largest and most powerful economy with GDP of \$17 trillion. The agricultural sector in USA is highly mechanized hence, the economy if being group among the top producers despite that just less than 3% of the total employed population is employed under the agricultural sector. The agricultural sector contributes only about 1% into the US GDP. USA is ranked as the World Largest Producer of Maize (corn), third in Wheat, fifth in Potatoes, tenth in Sugar and twelfth in the production of Rice.

The chart also shows that in 2016, 87.3% of food and beverages bought by US consumers were from domestic production. The remaining 12.7% were imported from Chile and France e.g. Wines, comparing the value of imports between 1993 and 2016, the value of imports almost doubled over the last two decades from 6.9% in 1993 to 12.7% in 2016. This is as a result of the growing demand by US consumers as well as their share of the US food and beverage dollar that have risen over time.

For imported inputs used in domestic production of food and beverages, it increased from 3.7% in 1993 to 4.7% in 2016. The USA imports about 15% of its overall food supply. The percentage of imported food and beverages in the USA economy for the year 2020 and 2022 is as follows:

Table 3.2

Items of Information	2020	2022
All imports	11.7%	5.6%
Food, feeds and beverages	13.2%	14.5%
Agricultural foods, feeds and beverages, excluding distilled beverages	14.0%	14.4%
Meat, poultry and other edible animal products	29.0%	29.0%
Fruits and fruit preparations including frozen juices	13.2%	13.2%
Vegetables and vegetables preparation	6.9%	6.9%
Food oil and oil seeds	45%	45.8%
Bakery and confectionery products	6.4%	6.4%

Source: second estimate released by the Bureau of Economic Analysis.

The US imports a good portion of its food supply from other countries, with a higher percentage increase in 2021 compared to 2022. This trend may continue due to global demand and supply chain factors.

Table 3.3

Percentage of imported input	2020	2022
Total US imports	\$2.8trillion	\$3.9trillion
Total US exports	\$2.1trillion	Not specified
US trade deficit	18.2% increase to \$681.7billion	Not specified
US imports as a percentage of GDP	Not specified	14.59%

Note below: search result were last updated in December 22, 2021.

In 2020, the US expenditure showed a high goods trade deficit (\$905.2 billion) with exports decreasing at more than double the rate of the decline in imports (-2.9% Vs.. -6.4%). The largest US export sectors including Air craft and Space craft, vehicle petroleum products and machinery. These four sectors accounted for 41% of total goods export in 2019 but were responsible for more than 70% of the overall export declined in 2020.

In 2022, the value of international US import of commodities amount to 3.96trillion US dollars, making the highest figure observed since the turn of the millennium.

At any rate, according to the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health in Agriculture Safety, approximately 2112626 full time workers were employed in production agriculture in the USA in 2019 and approximately 1.4 to 2.1 million hired crop workers are employed annually on crop farm in the US. Online source: <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki>.

Again, US as the top food exporter is also attributed to high crop yield and extensive agricultural infrastructure. Topping list for maize (corn), seed corn and rice. For instance, USA exported \$177 billion worth of agricultural goods in 2021.

USA produce enough food to feed 1.5 of the global population which is enough to feed 10 billion yet e are just over 7 billion currently. <https://usafacts.org/articles>. 21 March, 2023.

The problem is our food system, the way we produce, harvest, transport, process, market and consume food. 10 October, 2022. <https://news.thin-ink-net.weprodu...>

The top exports of USA are refined petroleum (\$83.38) petroleum gas (\$70.96), crude petroleum gas (\$67.6B) cars (\$55.4B) and integrated circuits (\$259B) exporting mostly to Canada (\$259B), Mexico (\$247B), China (\$151B), Japan (\$71.8B) and South Korea (\$66.4). <https://Dec.world.profile, country>.

With this trend and disparity between Nigerian economy and US economy over the years, viewing the agricultural sector, it will not be out of place to say that Nigeria government is still playing. It is high time this all important sector be attention technologically to revamp the economy, though the agricultural sector and secured a formidable food security for domestic consumption for export revenue and perhaps for employment for our youths.

For Indian economy, about 45% of the Indian population are into agriculture. Though the importance of agriculture has declined over the years, it remains an important sector contributing about 18% to the country's GDP it share to GDP has reduced from more than 30% in 1980's but the overall modernization, productivity an resources have tremendously increased. According to the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP), the Indian agricultural machinery and service sector has paved way for Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) equity inflows of \$365.79million (April, 2000 to Sept., 2014). Indians is the second largest producer of sugar cane, wheat rice, and maize and the sixth largest producer of potatoes.

The Russian agricultural sector employs about 10% of the entire population, accounts for 4% of \$2.05 trillion economy. The economy has experienced a transformation since the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991. This has made Russian economy to become a market based open economy different from an earlier Centrally Planned economy. Only 13% of Russia's land area is used for farming because of the constraints imposed by its climatic and geographical limitations.

However, from the total agricultural produce, 40% is from crop farming and the remaining 60% is from livestock, including wool, meat and dairy farming, Russian is the third largest producer of potatoes, fourth in wheat and twelfth in maize production.

The agricultural sector of the Brazil's economy employs about 15% of the population workforce and 30% of the land area for its agricultural activities. Brazil is the most popular South American economies. Though Brazil economy is mostly service sector economy, the agricultural sector contributes about 6% to its GDP of \$2.24 trillion and the largest world producer of sugar cane, third in the production of maize, ninth in the production of rice.

China agricultural sector employs $\frac{1}{3}$ of the China population workforce in the country. China is endowed with a large agricultural sector in terms of farming, forestry, animal husbandry and fisheries, that contributes 10% to its GDP. It has a special combination of an industrial and agricultural economy. World's factory for the massive manufacturing activities in the country and largest agricultural economy as well. Contribution of the agricultural sector to GDP has largely remained 10% over the years China is the World Largest Producer of wheat, rice and Potatoes. Second in maize and third in sugar cane production.

Looking at the demand and supply relationship world wide, we can consider wheat, rice, potatoes, maize (corn) and sugar cane as the most commonly produced food items and the 5 top commodities in the world when measured in tons. Sugar cane is the most produced product in the world. USA is also ranked among the top producers despite that just less than 3% of the US population is employed by the agricultural sector of USA economy.

The New Technology and its Challenges.

1. **Technical Knowhow:** challenges in the application of New Technology e.g. Lack of expert to manage and operate the machines for maximum, efficient and effective productivity. The New Technological equipment/facilities and technological knowhow have long replaced the use of crude implements of the agricultural and the manufacturing mode of production. The New Technology can as well be translated as agricultural mechanization and manufacturing industries. But much has not been achieved in this direction, in that the Nigeria economy is predominantly more of labour intensive rather than capital intensive. The nature of Capital Intensive off the new technology in the agricultural and manufacturing activities has negatively retarded the growth and development of these sectors. Between January and March, 2021 agricultural sector contributed 22.35% of the GDP over 70% of Nigerians engage in agricultural sector mainly at subsistence level. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/>
2. **Management and Leadership Problem:** our leaders don't have interest of people at heart i.e. to empower them economically especially in the agricultural and manufacturing sectors. This is so because when one is empowered economically (economic empowerment) one can get access to political power and change things for the better. Our leaders want our people to remain poor so that nobody challenges them. Policy implementation is also a critical issue in this regard. Most agricultural policies to change the sectors technologically are not given the desired attention, often times most policies are jettison and abandoned.

Other challenges include;

- Post processing of harvest problem
- Poor land tenure system
- Low level of irrigation farming
- Climatic change and land deforestation
- High production cost and
- Poor distribution of inputs
- Limited financing/credit facilities
- High poor harvest due to low storage facilities
- Lack of accessibility to market

These challenges have hampered agricultural productivity and its contribution to the country's GDP.

According to the minister of Agric and Rural Development Chief Audu Ogbe in 2018, mention about five (5) major problems facing agricultural production in Nigeria

- i. Lack of modernization/mechanization that is farmers should be provided with modern tools not crude implements
- ii. Lack of information/awareness; for instance, farmers need to know the right seed variety and planting method to get optimum yield.
- iii. Poor infrastructure; poor infrastructure discourage local and foreign investment.
- iv. Poor research and record keeping. No proper farm diary record

- v. Finance; for instance, 88% of Nigeria farmers are considered small family farmers. Also, 72% of Nigeria small holders live below the poverty line of USD 1.9 (691) a day. So lack of fund for expansion is a major problem.

4.1 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study is on New Technology in Agriculture and manufacturing sectors in Nigeria. The large and growing population in Nigeria is a potential for vibrant internal market for increased agricultural productivity, unfortunately reverse has been the case. However, the dwindling nature of the sector has been attributed to the emergence of the oil in large quantities. The use of crude implements in the agricultural sector in addition to the above factor have greatly hampered the agricultural productivity.

The manufacturing sector has been seen as a complementary sector to the agricultural sector, particularly as a source of raw materials to the manufacturing and industrial sector. The manufacturing sector serve as a market for the agricultural product. This forward and backward linkage between these two sectors call for great concern for New technology and development. The issue of technological knowhow, post processing of harvest problem, poor land tenure system etc. to mention but a few have hampered the growth of agricultural productivity in Nigeria.

Comparing Nigeria agricultural system to other agricultural economies worldwide such as USA, China, India, Brazil, Russia we discovered that the working population employed in the agricultural sector is not up to $\frac{1}{5}$ of the working population of Nigeria agricultural sector, except India that has up to 45% yet they have enough to eat and export to other countries in the world. For instance USA employed less than 3%, India about 45% Russia about 4%, Brazil about 15%, China $\frac{1}{3}$ of China population, but about 70% or even more than are employed in the Nigeria agricultural system, Nigeria still produce at subsistence level.

4.2 RECOMMENDATION

The reason that could be attributed to this disparity is the level of new technology, technological knowhow, including mechanization of the agricultural and the manufacturing sectors. Modalities should be put in place to imbibe with new technology and mechanization of the agricultural system. The manufacturing and the industrial sectors should be enhanced hand in hand with the agricultural sector for better productivity. Thousands of the unemployed youth should be encouraged to go into agriculture by providing an enabling environment with better facilities for the youth to embark agricultural system in the Nigeria economy.

Provision of machines, coveralls, safety boots, and hand glove, hard hat etc. should be made available to the youths just like the oil sector workers.

However, with improved varieties and production techniques, high level of technological knowhow, production is anticipated to increase.. <https://www.pwc.com/ng/en/assets/pdf/cassava-production-nigeria-report-2020>.

With population estimation of 400million by the year 2050, enhanced agricultural production through improved agricultural techniques/technological innovation is necessary to ensure food security and nutrition in the country. The various levels of government – local, state, and federal should pursue and ensure agricultural productivity beyond subsistence level. If agriculture is given priority and developed technologically like the oil sector, thousands of unemployed youths can be encouraged and channeled into all this important sector in Nigeria. This can bring about

reduction in unemployment, increase in productivity and output at the local level and there after can transcends to international market and increase in foreign exchange earnings and reserves.

The study of agriculture and its application technologically should be introduced as a general study course (GST) in Nigeria Universities. When the active agents (the labour force) is matched with the passive agents (natural resources) especially the agricultural sector, these combination can turn the Nigeria economy to food production centre, food security and nutritional needs.

References

- Adegeye, A.J. and Dittoh, J.S. (1985). *Essential of Agricultural Economics*, impact publishers Nig. Ltd. 164-177
- Adelman, T. (1984). Beyond export led growth, world development. (299): 937-949.
- Adubi, C.A (2004). Agriculture, it performance, problems and prospects. Democratic Government Development. In Bello Imam I.B and M.I. Obadan (Ed) *Management in Nigeria's Fourth Republic 1999-2003 CLGARDs*, 2004.
- Cervantes-Godoy, D and Dewbre, J. (2010). Economic importance of Agriculture for sustainable development and poverty reduction; Findings from a case study of Indonesia, paper presented to the Global Forum on Agriculture. 29-30 November, 2010. Policies for Agricultural Development, Poverty Reduction, and Food Security OECD Headquarters, Paris.
- Chavvin, N., Millangu, F. and Porto, G. (2012). Food production and consumption trends in Sub-Saharan Africa; prospects for the paper for African Human Development Reports. 1-74.
- CIA (2012). The world facebook. Retrieved March 3, 2013 from <https://www.cia.gov/library/publications/the-world-facebook/goes/ni.html>
- Ego, E.O. (2008). Macro-economic Environment and Agricultural Sector Growth in in Nigeria. *World J. Agric. Sci* (496) 781-786.
- Egwu, W.E.; Akubuilu CJC (2007). Agricultural policy, Development and Implementation in Akubuilu, CJC (Ed.) Chapter in *Book of Readings in Agricultural, Economics and Extension*.
- Fatola, T. and Heaton, M. (2008). *A history of Nigeria*. New York Cambridge University Press. Pp.183
- Ministry of Budget and National Planning (2017). *Nigeria Economic Recovery and Growth Plan. 2017-2020*. Pp(71).
- Ohale, L. (2007). MSc. Lecture Notes, University of PortHarcourt, Rivers State.
- Olayemi, J.K. (1998). *Agricultural Development Strategy; International Framework and Support*. Paper presented at the workshop on policy issues and planning in the Agricultural Sector, NCEMA. June 15-26, 1998.
- Olomola, A.S. (1998). *Analysis and Management of Agricultural Sector Performance and Inter-Sectional Linkages*. Paper Presented at Training Programme on Sectoral Policy Analysis and Management (NCEMA) June, 1998.

Payne (2000). The changing role of fisheries in development policy Natural Resources Perspectives. ODI/DFID.2000.

Sekunmade, A. (2009). The effect of petroleum dependency on agricultural trade in Nigeria. An Error Correlation Modeling (ECM) approach. Scientific Research and Essay. 4(11) 1385-1391.

Online Sources

<https://www.statista.com/statistics/>

<https://www.ta.org/cropsnew/cassava/>

<https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki>

[https://usafacts.org>articles.](https://usafacts.org/articles)

<https://news.thin-ink-net.weprodu>

<https://dec.world.profile,country>

<https://www.ers.usda.gov>

<https://www.pwc.com/ng/en/assets/pdf/cassava-production-nigeriareport.2020>